

CASES THAT NEGATIVELY AFFECT THE PREPARATION OF CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980314>

Annotation. This article describes situations that negatively affect the preparation of children for school education. Based on the conclusions drawn, proposals were developed.

Keywords: didactic Games, action games, educator's story, conversation, educational activities, excursions.

Introduction

A wide variety of games are used, along with observations made with the aim of expanding children's perceptions of ordinary phenomena and objects of nature. In these games, children gain experience of sensitivity, creative mastery of the acquired knowledge. When introducing children to nature, didactic character and creative games are used.

In didactic games, children determine in themselves the knowledge that objects and phenomena in nature have about animals and plants, musicianize, expand. Many games teach children to generalize as well as to classify. Didactic games contribute to the growth of memory, attention, observability. Teaches children to use new conditions from existing knowledge. Activates various mental processes. Enrich the vocabulary. Helps to educate children the skill of playing together. Game exercises teach to distinguish objects and phenomena according to their quality and characteristics. Grows observability. These are played with or part of a whole group of children. Game exercises are of particular importance in small and medium-sized groups. In the case of large groups, it is part of educational activities.

Action games of a naturalistic nature are associated with the behavior of animals imitating their way of life. Children acquire knowledge deeper in these games by imitating sounds to movements. Enjoying the game deepens the interest in nature in children.

In the game, Children reflect the visions received in the process of educational activities, excursions, everyday life. They acquire knowledge of the labor of adults in nature. In this, a creative attitude to work is formed in them. They realize the importance of the labor of adults in nature. Labor in nature. Child labor objects characteristics and qualities of plants the main stages of the development of their structural needs cultivation methods GET an idea of seasonal changes in plant life about animals, their external appearance needs, ways of acting, behavior, lifestyle and its seasonal changes. They learn to establish proportionality between the living environment and the animal's way of life in nature and caring for them in the corner of nature. The forms of Labor Organization and the methodology for their leadership become more complex throughout preschool education. Complication is determined due to the age possibilities of the child, as well as the growth of labor activity.

Oral methods. When introducing children to nature, a conversation is used from reading fiction books about nature from the story of the educator. In the use of oral methods, the

educator takes into account the ability of children to understand their speech, to focus on their long-term voluntary attention and the content given through the word, as well as whether children have vivid visions of this or that phenomenon or fact that is the subject of discussion, identification, systematization.

The story of the educator. Perception of a story is a rather complex mental activity for children. The fact that a child can hear and listen to adult speech in the course of a story that he will realize it on the basis of an oral image that he actively imagines enough vivid images the event in the story of the educator should correlate events and determine their relationship and understand the infallibility of the content of the story in comparison with his

Interview. From didactic tasks, the conversation is divided into two types – pre-held conversations and final conversations. These conversations can be of varying degrees in content: after one observes the observed objects in a narrow circle, the other covers a wide range of phenomena with the aim of systematizing a wide range of phenomena – children's knowledge of inanimate natural phenomena, plant life, animals, labor of people.

Reading fiction. A book about natural science, which is scientific in its content, is a kind of art at the same time. The natural science book gives children a rich matériel for the education of the right to know, observability, an obsession with knowledge.

Educational activities. Educational activities of introducing children to nature make it possible to consistently formulate knowledge, referring to the capabilities of children as well as the features of the surrounding nature. In educational activities under the guidance of an educator, elementary knowledge is formed in accordance with the requirements of the program in all children of the group. Basic knowledge processes and children's abilities are cultivated in a certain system and consistency. In everyday life, personal knowledge of children is accumulated during observation, play, work. Educational activities make it possible to identify and systematize them.

Educational function of educational activities. This is the volume of knowledge that children should be given or identified in educational activities and concretized. This can again be facilitated by the formation of children's interests in knowing nature. Educational tasks that are solved in educational activities. Formation of a positive careful, caring attitude towards nature. It is oriented towards the cultivation of an aesthetic attitude to nature. When preparing for educational activities and conducting it, it is important to correctly determine the method of the structure of educational activities. The choice of method depends on the nature of educational tasks, the characteristics of the natural object, as well as the age of the children. During educational activities, it is important to involve all children in the task. At the end of educational activities, according to the rule, the educator pedagogically evaluates the qualifications and skills of children, their relationship to educational activities, interests. The differentiation of grades will depend on the age of the children.

Tours. The excursion is one of the types of educational activities that introduce children to nature. During excursions, the child can see how the observation of natural phenomena in natural conditions changes nature in accordance with the requirements of human life and how nature serves people. The advantage of excursion activities is again that in IT children will have the opportunity to see plants and animals, the environment in which they live. Thanks to excursions, observation in children, interest in changing nature grows. They are used to carefully observing the object and noting its character traits.

The beauty of nature evokes deep feelings in children, leaving an indelible impression. Promotes the growth of aesthetic emotions. On this basis, love for nature is again formed, a careful attitude towards it, love for the motherland.

Organizing excursions. The excursion is used as a type of educational activity in medium, large, as well as in preparatory groups. For each excursion, the content of the program is determined, which all children are obliged to occupy.

Work in everyday life. Observations in educational activities and excursions are carried out in close contact with everyday life, as well as with other forms.

Walks. Walks are widely used to introduce children to nature. During walks, the educator will have the opportunity to familiarize himself with the phenomena of nature, for which the imagination of children requires a special period for its formation. Children are introduced to the melting of snow, bulging of buds, the appearance of grass and so on. On walks, it is possible to organize a variety of games with natural materials such as kum, clay, water, ice, leaf, etc. In preschool children, sensory experience is rich, they see natural phenomena in natural conditions in all communication and relationships. Walks are of interest to children, they are given a lot of joy, and dividing in a relationship with nature gives pleasure. The acquisition of comprehensive knowledge of the child by introducing a preschool child to nature the development of psychic processes, the growth of abilities, the formation of a scientific worldview, the assimilation of moral qualities, positive behavior habits contribute to the development of aesthetic emotions. The beauty of nature evokes deep feelings in children, gives an indelible impression, promotes the growth of aesthetic emotions. On this basis, love for Mother Nature, careful attitude towards it, interest in the study of nature (to living and inanimate nature) grows, forming love for the motherland.

Discussion and results

The preschool educational organization for visual activities program and the school visual arts program provide for the development of creative abilities and representations in children in relation to tevarak-environment, the education of aesthetic attitude in children of art. In pre-school activities, the tasks required for successful schooling are solved. In the process of painting, appliqué, clay works, such as analysis, synthesis, repetition, concretization of reasoning in children are formed. Also, in these processes, children are used to working in a team, subjecting their movement to the movement of their comrades. Educational activities of visual activity in the children's preschool educational organization form the necessary qualifications and skills in children, educational activities. These are: listening to the assignment and keeping in mind the execution between known times to plan and evaluate their work, to bring the work started to an end, to find mistakes and shortcomings and to correct it, to keep the weapons of the material and the workplace in order, among others.

The inspections carried out by educators show that such a system of education in a preschool organization affects the preparation of children for school. Also, other psychologists E.A. The processes of studying the imaging activities of schoolchildren by Labunsky and others indicate that the structure of visual arts lessons in the school is organized taking them into account based on the knowledge, qualifications and skills that children receive in the MTT. In educational activities of visual activity in preschool educational organizations, children perform mainly practical work, get acquainted with the works of SA'nat in the process of storytelling by painting, reviewing the illustrations in the book, the types of Visual Arts in

school get to know more deeply with the works of Color Image, graphic, sculpture and decorative arts in the preschool educational organization. In the organization of preschool education, great importance is attached to all educational activities. The school, on the other hand, offers painting (depending on nature) subject-based and decorative types of Fine Arts classes. In this, drawing according to the nature of the subject painting will have the importance of the subject of study. Practical work on clay appliqué, construction-making works at school are included in manual labor. Analysis of the elementary school visual arts program, the work shows that in addition to the introduction of subject, painting training tasks much more murakablik, some repetition work was introduced on the MTT program. In the 1st grade, children learn to identify objects with a structure such as a circle, square, turtleneck, oval, the task set in front of children in the MTT is set according to the mastery of drawing techniques. This is due to the fact that not all children come to school from the MTT, and therefore work with children should be started with the knowledge gained in the preparatory group until they come to school. Drawing based on the subject takes place as a continuation of the meaningful drawing that takes place in the MTT. Children observe and examine the tevarak-surrounding phenomena and objects, and then draw them based on their memories. Students describe meaningful connections between objects by miniaturizing distant objects.

Decorative painting tasks are set in the school according to technical procedures, that is, in combination with representation in the sequence of the pattern structure, the use of auxiliary lines and the use of elements of folk applied decorative art in their work are learned in the course of a lesson conversation about art. Methods for teaching children to fine arts should be used taking into account the characteristics of children. There is much affinity between the working characteristics of older preschool children and younger students. Therefore, there is also a lot of similarity between the methods of teaching one or another. At school, it is close to showing some element of the teacher's picture and explaining in this process the teacher's methods of work. In school, the sequence of the work appears to be orderly-if the structure of the object to be described is simple, the order is deleted after the descent. When a subject with a complex structure is described, however, they are described sequentially by the teacher's display on the board. The teacher shows the general outline of the object by lightly marking it with the tip of the pencil and also marking its width by marking its height. Then the reader compares the subject with his drawing with the nature and determines its parts, shape and, corrects.

The work uses a set of images for display and analysis in the process, color illustrations in children's booklets, as well as individual pictures of a learning character. Each lesson on painting begins with the conversation and explanation of the teacher and the explanation of what to start the painting. In the transition to practical execution of work, the teacher reminds the children of the rules and ways of drawing in an orderly manner. The requirements for the work or painting of children of older preschool age and small schoolchildren are very close to each other. When analyzing the work of children, it is necessary to draw attention to the proportion, construction, dependence of parts, color and compositional structure of the subject. Thus, the successful resolution of educational issues in primary classes, children's preschool education is inextricably linked with the educational activities of the image carried out in the organization. The preparation of children for school is carried out in preschool educational organizations. Preschool organizations place great emphasis on drawing on large

groups of observations, as the object is a step in preparing children to paint by nature. This thing develops visual memory in children, sometimes the object helps to correctly describe it as a kind in children. Children learn to control their character and hand strength in the educational activities of the pictorial activities carried out in the group, the free use of pencils, furs. Mastering this skill develops in children the characteristics of light, free uniform movement of the hand. In the process of drawing objects of different shapes, sizes, different proportions, children learn to move in accordance with the need to maintain orientation, movement, length of the object, depending on the nature of the object's work. Children are used to the clean and orderly use of the material visual activities carried out in the preschool educational organization they are used to keeping them clean only using the necessary materials, planning ways to use them. This educational activity develops attention, visual memory in children. In the preparatory group of the children's preschool organization, depending on the nature, the requirements for drawing or painting increase, and these requirements approach the school requirement. Children try to analyze Natura by putting the entire general form on raw paper, comparing the picture to Natura, correcting mistakes and shortcomings, resembling Natura. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

Showing the sequence of work when describing by nature, it is carried out only at the initial stage of learning in the preparatory and large group of children's preschool educational organization. Constant use in rendering makes children get used to working the picture mechanically. Describing children by nature all this affects the success of educational activities in all classes, especially in labor classes.

Conclusion

Children's educational activities of visual activity help children to be able to find or see geometric shapes, to call them terms, to get acquainted with the size of the width, spontaneity, height, spatial arrangement of parts in relation to each other, to thoroughly master elementary mathematical concepts of school in 1st grade. In the children's preschool organization, building-making from the necessary materials forms eye-popping in children and helps children master or master technical classes at school. Drawing according to the nature of a large group of preschool educational organizations, children learn to independently choose the means of describing the subject in their own way, analyzing the spatial characteristics of the subject, making the main distinction in logical thinking, observation in training. And all this is necessary in the process of studying at school. Thus, in the training of visual activity, artistic taste and creative abilities in children grow, through which they are prepared to study at school.

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